

BogTalk

Insights from
engagement with land
managers in the High
Peak.

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This short report outlines insights from an engagement process with land managers in the High Peak that took place in October 2024. The work was delivered under Theme 3 of the RENEW programme. The aim was to create a space for deliberation on environmental land management issues, explore challenges to, and identify solutions for, effective nature conservation and restoration practices in the High Peak, particularly for the management of peatlands. In what follows, we detail the process and the insights learned from it.

Insights from engagement with land managers in the High Peak.

The Context

The Peak District is home to the first UK national park. It contains a range of landscapes and habitats of national, and sometimes international, significance with 36% of the land being currently SSSI-designated.¹ The area includes a large proportion of the upland peat in England with moorland making up 30% of the total area.

Around 87% of the land in the Peak District is farmed.² Ownership of the land in the area is complex and fragmented, comprising major landowners, several of which are conservation organisations like the National Trust and RSPB, and a variety of individual landholdings. More than half of upland farms in the Peak District are owner-occupied, with around 45% of farms falling under a tenancy agreement.³

The High Peak reflects much of this complex picture, with the majority of the land managed for agriculture,⁴ and involving a mix of major landowners, individual landholdings and tenant farmers. The High Peak is also home to 89% of the Peak District's blanket bogs, which feature high on the vulnerability scale.⁵

¹ Peak District National Park (2021) *State of the Park Report*. Available here: [://reports.peakdistrict.gov.uk/sotpr/docs/people-&-farming/other-land-management.html](https://reports.peakdistrict.gov.uk/sotpr/docs/people-&-farming/other-land-management.html)

² *State of the Park Report*: <https://reports.peakdistrict.gov.uk/sotpr/>

³ *State of the Park Report*: <https://reports.peakdistrict.gov.uk/sotpr/>

⁴ High Peak Brorough Council (2022) High Peak: Agriculture and Land Use Analysis. Available here: https://www.highpeak.gov.uk/media/8301/High-Peak---Agriculture-and-Land-Use-Analysis/pdf/High_Peak_-_Agriculture_and_Land_Use_Analysis_v1.1.pdf?m=1683875453377

⁵ *State of the Park Report*: <https://reports.peakdistrict.gov.uk/sotpr/>

The Engagement Process

What did the process set out to achieve?

The work aimed to create a space for deliberation on environmental land management issues, explore related challenges, and identify solutions for more effective nature conservation and restoration practices in the High Peak. The process allowed participants to freely express their views and engage in collective problem-solving. More concretely, this approach entailed encouraging participants to agree on a range of issues, such as the key concerns they currently hold and collectively deliberate on solutions to the problems identified over the course of the meetings.

How was the process structured and organized?

The work was undertaken in October 2024, over three meetings of around three hours each. The number of participants at the deliberative fora varied between nine and twelve. A core of eight attended all meetings. The total number of participants was twelve.

The first forum adopted an open-ended format, encouraging participants to express key concerns High Peak farmers hold, regarding environmental land management in the area. They were prompted to envision how economic activities such as food production and tourism can coexist with nature recovery goals in the future in the High Peak. The second forum invited participants to provide more details around the key concerns raised during the first forum and identify practical ways of addressing those concerns. Forum three was devoted to a discussion over different fictional agri-environment scheme scenarios, building on the practical solutions identified in forum two.

Who participated?

The engagement process involved members of the Peakland Environmental Farmers (PEF) group. The number of attendees was intentionally kept small to allow participants to have sufficient time to engage in the discussions and reflect on views and solutions.

The sample comprised a mix of sheep farmers (tenants and owner-occupiers), landowners, and gamekeepers, all from, or at close proximity to, the High Peak. Several participants owned and/or managed land in or in close proximity to peatland and SSSI-designated areas.

Challenges Identified by Land Managers

At the first meeting, participants were encouraged to reflect on management practices they had been applying on their land, either as part of their SSSI designation or by agri-environment schemes they had historically adopted. Reflections gathered during the first meeting were organised in a number of themes which consequently served as a basis for discussions. During the second meeting participants were encouraged to provide greater detail on the issues they had raised and deliberate on solutions. Participants' suggestions on possible solutions were synthesised to form the prescriptions of hypothetical alternative agri-environmental schemes which participants had the opportunity to consider and evaluate during the third meeting. What follows is a review of the challenges identified throughout the deliberations.

Role of land managers in nature recovery

Land managers play an essential role in delivering environmental goods and services. Their decisions significantly impact on the biophysical conditions of the land they oversee, making them a key stakeholder when it comes to implementing environmental land management prescriptions of any sort. Our participants had much to say about the way they view this role. They are keen to get many of the actions they take to recover nature better recognised and be given more opportunities to draw on their knowledge for meeting environmental objectives.

One key concern expressed by participants was the fact that what they already do in terms of nature recovery is not being sufficiently recognised by conservation organisations. For example, many insisted that the way they manage their land contributes to the creation of habitats for endangered species like lapwings and curlews.

Others claimed that they have accumulated valuable knowledge of their land, which existing agri-environment schemes do not allow them to draw on. They accepted that they can sometimes be given a choice of actions, like in the case of the Sustainable Farming Incentive scheme, but claimed that a menu of options does not give them enough opportunities to use that knowledge. They would rather be given an ecological outcome and freely choose the actions they think are best to achieve it.

Furthermore, they felt like what they do on their land as farmers or grouse managers is often viewed as a problem for nature recovery by conservation organisations. They noted feeling distrusted by those organisations.

They wished more could be done to make environmental land management practices more compatible with farming practices.

Accountability

A recurrent theme raised by participants was around accountability. Many land managers felt that they were often made to feel accountable for their decisions and blamed for failures in delivering benefits for nature. In contrast they believed that conservation organisations, which often experiment with management practices, do not receive equivalent scrutiny.

Such a concern was expressed alongside feelings of powerlessness in decision-making and the absence of the farming voice in key decisions around environmental land management. Participants expressed these feelings in different ways. Some claimed they feel excluded from decision-making processes related to environmental land management. Here they take issue with what they view as a lack of on-the-ground engagement with land managers. There was a strong sense that the perspective of farmers is often treated as a minority voice that is not as important or valuable as the perspective of conservation organisations.

Finally, land managers deplored what they view as a lack of institutional memory, absence of 'boots on the ground,' and high staff turnover. This, they claimed, makes it difficult for conservation organisations to understand what land managers do on their land and prevents them from knowing what nature recovery actions have and have not failed.

Local and scientific knowledge

Land managers involved in the deliberations took issue with what they regard as the 'one-size-fits-all' approach to environmental land management. They expressed concerns at what

they see as insufficient attention paid to the conditions and configurations of a particular landscape or piece of land in environmental prescriptions.

Participants were also concerned that local knowledge is not valued equally with scientific knowledge, which is often regarded as superior. They noted the absence of opportunities to share both the knowledge gathered over generations of land stewardship and the ongoing efforts of land managers to implement environmental prescriptions.

Communications

A final theme observed by land managers has to do with the way conservation bodies communicate with them. In particular, they noted a lack of effective and supportive channels, highlighting that it was challenging to get speedy responses to queries.

They also commented on the lack of appropriate communication around changes to environmental prescriptions, noting the difficulties in understanding the rationale behind those changes, particularly when those are in opposition to previous prescriptions.

Finally, they deplored what they view as a lack of understanding of what land managers do on their land by conservation organisations. This, they argue, has to do with what they perceive as a lack of on-the-ground visits by those organisations, which could give them the opportunity to show and explain what they do on their land.

Designing the Ideal Agri-Environment Scheme

The third and final meeting was devoted to deliberations over different agri-environment scheme scenarios. Agri-environment schemes play a key role in environmental land management in England. Getting those schemes right is therefore imperative for effective nature conservation and restoration. For this reason, the last deliberative forum of the project was spent discussing a range of agri-environment scheme scenarios and encouraging participants to discuss their merits and limitations. At the end, participants deliberated on what they thought the ideal scheme ought to look like. They identified the following suggested features:

- Introduce something akin to a payment-by-results format where land managers are rewarded for meeting agreed outcomes.
- Being financially compensated for meeting an environmental outcome comes with risks which land managers do not have control over, such as weather events.
- Participants therefore stressed the importance of combining the reward for progress in meeting an outcome with an annual base payment.
- They also highlighted the importance of incentivizing the creation of landscape-scale groups for the design of bespoke environmental plans, and to enable knowledge-sharing around actions taken for meeting ecological outcomes.

- A conservation organization trusted by the farmer group could provide support and guidance for the design of the plan and delivery of outcomes.
- They envisioned individual outcomes for each land manager participating in this landscape-scale scheme.

Suggested Solutions

A key focus of each meeting, and particularly the second and third meetings, was on deliberations around ways to improve the delivery of environmental land management in the High Peak from the perspective of the participating land managers. The suggestions included the following:

- It is of fundamental importance that nature conservation organisations recognize the work land managers do for nature.
- Greater transparency and better communication around changes in land management practices and environmental prescriptions could increase their perceived legitimacy.
- Giving land managers more opportunities to explain what they do on their land and provide feedback on the nature recovery actions they have taken could enhance the effectiveness of nature recovery actions.
- Greater involvement of land managers in decision-making processes within conservation organisations will help enhance the legitimacy of environmental management practices within the farming community.
- Fostering long-term relationships between land managers and representatives of conservation groups could help create a mutually supportive environment with positive effects on nature recovery.
- An outcome-based agri-environmental scheme could give land managers more freedom in decision-making and help develop a sense of ownership and responsibility over nature recovery actions.
- Ensuring that environmental prescriptions, such as stocking rates, are adapted to land conditions and configurations could help enhance their effectiveness while improving the compatibility of nature recovery actions with farming practices.

Conclusion

Many of the suggestions participants made over the course of the engagement process were guided by a sense that their experiences, observations, and knowledge ought to play a much larger role in environmental land management. They expressed a strong and widely shared appetite for a greater integration of their local knowledge with scientific expertise. This could be done through a range of measures such as giving land managers opportunities to provide feedback on environmental prescriptions, designing outcome-based environmental plans, or playing a more important role in designing environmental prescriptions.

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